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Research Article

**INCIDENCE OF A 2ND MESIO-BUCCAL CANAL IN THE
FIRST PERMANENT MOLAR OF MAXILLA****Fatima Kanwal¹, Sadiq ullah², Kanwal Safeer³**
^{1,2,3} Sardar Begum Dental College and Hospital, Peshawar**Article Received:** October 2020 **Accepted:** November 2020 **Published:** December 2020**Abstract:**

Introduction: The complexity of the root canal morphology leads to the risk of endodontic treatment failure due to the missed canal. The availability of Cone-beam Computed Tomography (CBCT) contributed to the evaluation of the second mesio-buccal canals in the maxillary first molars.

Aim: To investigate the presence of the second buccal canals (MB2), classify the morphology of the canals according to the Vertucci classification, and measure the distance between the MB1 and MB2 channels.

Materials and Methods: 72 CBCT scans, including 115 permanent first maxillary molars, were assessed by an endodontist and an oral radiologist separately using Dicom software to examine the morphology of the buccal root canal. The oral radiologist and endodontist individually assessed scans in frontal, axial and oblique views to examine the canal configuration. The Vertucci classification was used to classify the canal configurations. Statistical tests were performed to assess gender variability and difference on the side of the curve.

Results: out of 115 assessed images; 30.4% of the samples had a second mesiobuccal canal. The most common canal configuration was type I (60.9%) in the mesio-buccal root. The mean distance between MB1 and MB2 channels was 2.39 mm in women and 2.56 mm in men.

Conclusion: The presence of a second canal in the mesio-buccal root of the maxillary permanent molar is significant in patients. CBCT can be an effective tool for detecting the MB2 canal and other complexities of the canal system to achieve clinical success.

Keywords: CBCT, Endodontics, Buccal canal, Vertucci classification

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INTRODUCTION:

The first maxillary molar is one of the longest standing teeth in the dental arch and is used as an occlusion and anchor key in most orthodontic procedures [1-2]. However, they are prone to various injuries, such as tooth decay, abrasion, etc. The tooth is very important in the chewing process and overall bite balance; therefore, it is strategically important to keep the tooth as far as possible in the dental arch, which often requires endodontic treatment [3-4].

The success of endodontic treatment is attributed to the proper cleaning, disinfection, shaping and three-dimensional sealing of the root canal system. This process is routinely questioned due to the complexity of the root canal morphology. Knowledge of root canal morphology is a key factor in a successful treatment outcome [5-6]. Maxillary molars have a complex morphology that is characterized by the highest rate of clinical failure due to the omission of the second buccal canal with significant differences in the morphology of the buccal root. Numerous studies have been carried out to investigate the root canal configuration of the first maxillary molars using both in vitro and in vivo methods such as staining and canal cleansing techniques, contrast-enhanced radiography, computed tomography, intraoral periapical images, dentin cavity under magnification, clinical operating microscope, ultrasound and cone-beam computed tomography (CBCT) imaging methods [7-8]. Of all of them later, five have been used in clinical practice, and CBCT is considered the gold standard. CBCT is helpful for clinicians to identify all channels and their configuration in a clinical scenario [9]. The aim of this study is to evaluate the presence of a second buccal canal in the mesobuccal root, to classify the canals according to Vertucci, and to measure the distance between the first and second buccal canals using CBCT images.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

A retrospective study was conducted in the Orthodontics department of Sardar Begum Dental

College and Hospital, Peshawar for one-year duration from March 2019 to March 2020. The CBCT was performed for diagnostic or treatment planning purposes. CBCT scans were performed on patients according to ALARA principles on a Carestream CS9300 machine (USA). The field of view (FOV) of the machine was 17 x 13.5 cm. Scans were performed in the endo, perio, or 5x5 cm, 10x5 cm or 10x10 cm implantation modes. Patients received a surface product dose of 315 mGY.cm² to 956 mGY.cm² depending on the patient's body composition. In total, 72 scans were selected based on the inclusion criteria with 115 permanent first molars on one or both sides of the maxillary arch. Selected respondents were in the age range of 16-60 years. Scans were excluded if the tooth showed incomplete root development, root fused, developmental anomaly, root canal or clogged root canal, crown reconstruction, root resorption, or significant loss of tooth crown structure. Blurred or unclear images are also excluded. The data was anonymised prior to the evaluation. Images were assessed with Dicom CS 3D imaging software version 3.5. A voxel size of 180 µm was chosen to standardize the data across all scans. The oral radiologist and endodontist individually assessed scans in frontal, axial and oblique views to check the morphology of the canals (Fig. 1), assess the presence of the MB2 canal, classify the canals based on the Vertucci classification (Fig. 2) and measure the distance between the MB1 and MB2 Channels if they occur at the pulp floor. Data was recorded in Excel spreadsheet and statistically analyzed with the SPSS 20 software. Statistical tests were performed using a chi-square test to check the relationship between the M2 channel and the sex and arc side. Independent Student's t-test was used to compare the statistical difference between the distance between the channels and the sex. The significance level was set at $p < 0.05$. The Kappa test was performed to check the credibility between the observers between the oral radiologist and the endodontist. Cronbach's alpha test was performed to test the inter-observer reliability in measuring the distance between the MB1 and MB2 channels.

Figure 1: CBCT scans
Vertucci's Classification of root canal morphology

Type	Description	Configuration
Type I	A single canal from pulp chamber to the canal terminus	1-1
Type II	Two separate canals leaving the chamber but merging short of the canal terminus to form a single canal	2-1
Type III	A single canal that divides into two and subsequently merges to exit as one	1-2-1
Type IV	Two distinct canals from pulp chamber to the canal terminus	2-2
Type V	A single canal leaving the chamber and dividing into two separate canals at the canal terminus	1-2
Type VI	Two separate canals leaving the pulp chamber, merging in the body of the root, and dividing again into two distinct canals short of the canal terminus	2-1-2
Type VII	A single canal that divides, merges and exits into two distinct canals short of the canal terminus	1-2-1-2
Type VIII	Three distinct canals from pulp chamber to the canal terminus	3-3

Figure 2: Diagrammatic representation of Vertucci's classification

RESULTS:

A total of 115 samples of the maxillary first molar were observed on 72 CBCT scans. Of all, 53.9% were right and 46.1% were left-sided from the first molar.

The samples were 55.56% male and 44.44% female. The mean age of the sample was 33.53 years (SD 14.60) in the range of 16-60 years. The study showed that 30.4% of the first maxillary molars showed the

presence of the MB2 channel in the intra-buccal root. The most common channel configuration was type I Vertucci (60.9%) followed by type II (19.1%), type IV (7.8%) (Figure 1). Types V and VI were not found in any of the samples. The mean distance between the

intra-buccal-1 (MB1) and intra-buccal-2 (MB2) canals was 2.56 mm in men and 2.39 mm in women. There was no significant difference between the distance between the canals and the sex ($p = 0.506$) (Table 1).

Graph 1: Frequency of types of canal configuration (%)

Table 1: t-Test of significance for comparison of distance between canals Vs gender

	Mean Distance (mm)	SD	t-Value	p-Value
Female	2.39	0.75	-0.673	0.506 (NS)
Male	2.56	0.65		

Table 2: Association between M2 canal and gender

MB2 Canal	Gender		Total	X2	p-Value
	Female	Male			
Present	11	24	35	2.199	0.138 (NS)
	22.9%	35.8%	30.4%		
Absent	37	43	80		
	77.1%	64.2%	69.6%		
Total	48	67	115		

Table 3: Association between M2 canal and side

MB2 Canal	Maxillary First Molar		Total	X2	p-Value
	Right	Left			
Present	18	17	35	0.125	0.724 (NS)
	29.6%	32.1%	30.4%		
Absent	44	36	80		
	67.9%	69.6%	71.0%		
Total	62	53	115		

There was no statistically significant relationship between the presence or absence of the MB2 channel and gender ($p = 0.138$; Chi-square = 2.199) and sides ($p = 0.724$; Chi-square = 0.125) (Table 2, 3).

Inter-observer agreement was high for the presence or absence of the MB2 channel (Kappa = 0.918, $p < 0.001$) and the distance between MB1 and MB2 (Chronbach alpha = 0.976).

Table 4: Occurrence of MB2 canal in maxillary first molar in various studies

Investigator	Year	N	Model	%
Weine <i>et al</i>	1969	208	in vitro	62
Pineda	1973	245	in vitro	54.3
Hartwell & Belizzi	1982	1976	in vitro	18.6
Weller & Hartwell	1989	1134	in vitro	39.1
Kulild & Peters	1990	83	in vitro	95.2
Fogel <i>et al</i>	1994	208	in vivo	71.2
Stropko	1999	1732	in vivo	73.2
Sempira & Hartwell	2000	200	in vivo	33.1
Buhrley <i>et al</i>	2002	660	in vivo	93
Baldassari-Cruz <i>et al</i>	2002	39	in vitro	90
Coutinho Filho <i>et al</i>	2006	108	in vitro	90.7
Smadi & Khraisat	2007	100	in vitro	77.32
Alaçam <i>et al</i>	2008	100	in vitro	82
Hartmann <i>et al</i>	2009	65	in vitro	29.2
Baratto Filho <i>et al</i>	2009	100	in vitro & in vivo	67.14
Blattner <i>et al</i>	2010	20	in vitro	68.4
Pardo <i>et al</i>	2012	42	in vitro	23.81
Shrestha <i>et al</i>	2017	115	in vitro	30.4

Table 5: Canal configuration in mesiobuccal root of maxillary first molar in various studies

Investigator	Year	N	Country	Study Technique	Type I	Type II	Type III	Type IV
Weine	1969	208	USA	Vertical Sectioning	48.5	37.5	14.0	0
Pineda	1973	262	Mexico	Radiographic	39.3	12.2	35.7	12.8
Seldberg	1973	100	USA	Horizontal Sectioning	38.0	37.0	25.0	0
Evenot	1980	378	France	Radiographic and microscopic	28.8	23.5	38.8	8.8
Vertucci	1984	100	USA	Decalcified & decayed	45.0	37.0	18.0	0
Weine <i>et al</i>	1996	300	Japan	Files in extracted teeth	42.0	24.2	30.4	3.4
Shrestha <i>et al</i>	2017	115	Nepal	CBCT	60.9	19.1	5.2	7.8

DISCUSSION:

The morphological complexity of the maxillary first molar often leads to failure in the identification and location of the second subcutaneous canal, leading to endodontic treatment failure⁹⁻¹⁰. Different studies have described the different occurrence of the MB2 canal in the maxillary first permanent molar. Hartwell *et al*. Reported 40-95%, Weine *et al*. 51%, Buhrley *et al*. 93%, Pardo *et al*. 23.81% [11]. In this study, the presence of the MB2 channel was found in 30.4%,

which is consistent with the research by Hartmann *et al*. Z 29.2%. A summary of the literature on the prevalence of MB2 in the maxillary molar is summarized in Table 4. The variation in the results across studies was attributed to differences in age, gender, ethnicity / race, procedures, and study conditions. Alaçam *et al*. Compared direct observation, microscope, a combination of microscopic and ultrasonic methods, and preparation techniques for MB2 evaluation. The results were 62%,

67%, 74%, and 82%, respectively, showing a difference in the results. Pardo et al. Compared the effectiveness of three methods of channel identification; namely CBCT, clinical analysis and operating microscope, and revealed that CBCT is the best channel search tool. In this study, channel configurations were identified according to the Vertucci classification system with 60.9% of the most common type being type I. However, Faramarzi et al. Found that the type II channel configuration was 71.3% most common [12-13]. According to Rwenyonyi et al; Type I was most often accounted for at 75.1-100%. Lists of various literature regarding channel configuration are presented in Table 5.

The MB2 channel opening in the pulpal root of the buccal root is usually located in the developmental groove on an approximate line between the MB1 and the palatal opening, parallel to the mesial marginal edge. In this study, it was found that the maximum and minimum distance between the MB1 and MB2 holes is 3.80 mm and 1.40 mm, respectively, with an average value of 2.39 mm and 2.56 mm in women and men, respectively [14]. These values are in line with Faramarzi et al., With a maximum and minimum distance of 4mm and 1.5mm respectively. Zhang et al. Found that the MB2 canal lies less than 1 mm mesially to the MB-P line and 2 mm palatally to the MB outlet. Moreover, there was no statistically significant relationship between the sex groups and bilateral sides in the occurrence of the MB2 channel. These findings are consistent with the studies by Das et al [15].

CONCLUSION:

The presence of a second canal in the mesio-buccal root of a permanent maxillary molar is significant and amounts to 30.4% in the sample of patients. Therefore, physicians should assume the presence of the MB2 channel during endodontic surgery to optimize the treatment outcome. Physicians should examine a distance of 1.4-3.8 mm from the palatal side at the imaginary line joining the MB1 and the palatal opening to access the MB2 orifice. Conventional x-rays usually do not show the MB2 channel; thus, CBCT is the gold standard for the diagnosis of complex, questionable and retreatment of missed channels.

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